

**Population status of the endangered giant Mexican limpet *Scutellastra mexicana*
(Broderip & Sowerby, 1829) in the central Mexican Pacific.**

Abbreviated title: Evaluation of the giant Mexican limpet *Scutellastra mexicana* in the Central Pacific

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Population status of the endangered giant Mexican limpet *Scutellastra mexicana* (Broderip & Sowerby, 1829) in the central Mexican Pacific.

Abstract

1. *Scutellastra mexicana* is the largest species of giant limpet in the world. The species is distributed along the tropical Mexican Pacific and is now considered extinct in some areas of the region.
2. In prehispanic Mexico, this mollusk was used for ornamentation and in dedicatory offerings. More recently, its meat has been highly valued for human consumption. During the 1970s and 1980s, overexploitation of this resource caused the population to decrease drastically.
3. This study is a report on the population status of the giant Mexican limpet *Scutellastra mexicana* on the Mexican Pacific coast. Free divers explored the rocky southern coast of Jalisco, Mexico, for the presence of specimens. A total of 404 limpets were identified at 18 sampling sites in Bahía de Navidad; sizes ranged from 7.0 to 26.5 cm curve length and from 5.2 to 24.0 cm curve width.
4. Currently, *Scutellastra mexicana* is protected under Mexican law. However, the species is not listed as endangered by any international wildlife protection and conservation group. This may be due to the dearth of information on this species' population dynamics over time in the Mexican Pacific and the lack of interest in this resource due to the fact that it is a non-charismatic species.

Keywords: Mollusk, *Scutellastra mexicana*, giant limpet, population, Central Pacific, endangered species, overexploitation

1. Introduction

The giant Mexican limpet *Scutellastra mexicana* (Broderip & Sowerby, 1829) is a marine mollusk belonging to the class Gastropoda and the family Patellidae (ITIS, 2018) (Fig. 1). The species is distributed in the tropical waters of the Pacific Ocean from Mexico to Paita, Peru (Keen, 1971). In contrast, the other species belonging to this family have antitropical

distributions (Powell, 1973; Ridgway, Reid, Taylor, Branch, & Hodgson, 1998). *S. mexicana* inhabits rocky areas of the lower intertidal and subtidal zones, strongly adhering to the substrate in places with intense swells. The soft part of the organism is black with yellowish white speckles. The shell's interior is opaque white while the exterior is typically eroded by epibionts, leaving few visible ridges. The shell is broadly conical, measuring up to 35.5 cm total length, making this the largest limpet species in the world (Espinosa & Rivera-Ingraham, 2017; Keen, 1971; Powell, 1973).

In prehispanic Mexico, this mollusk was used for food, as a burial offering, and for ornamentation (Feinman & Nicholas, 2000; Melgar-Tisoc, 2007). The species was intensely exploited for commercial purposes during the 1970s and 1980s as its meat is highly valued for human consumption (Ríos-Jara et al., 2001; Ríos-Jara, Pérez-Peña, López-Uriarte, Enciso-Padilla, & Juárez-Carrillo, 2006), (Fig. 2). This fishery developed primarily along the coasts of the central Pacific; however, a total annual catch of approximately 100 t was reported by a single fishing cooperative on the coast of Michoacan for the year 1982 (Gorrostieta-Hurtado & Trujillo-Toledo, 2012). Anecdotal reports indicate that this species' abundance and the size of individual specimens have sharply decreased. However, recent data on this species are necessary to confirm these reports.

The scarce data currently available on this mollusk species consist of records of its presence throughout the Mexican Pacific as reported in taxonomic lists for the coasts of Jalisco and Colima (Esqueda-González, 1995; Esqueda-González, Ríos-Jara, Michel-Morfin, & Landa-Jaime, 2000; Landa-Jaime, Michel-Morfin, Arciniega-Flores, Castillo-Vargasmachuca, & Saucedo-Lozano, 2013; Ríos Jara et al., 2001, 2006) as well as Michoacan (Fuentes-Farías, Villarroel Melo, & Solís-Marín, 2005; Holguin-Quñones, 2006) and Oaxaca (Bastida-Zavala et al., 2013). On the islands of the Mexican Pacific, its presence has been reported in the Islas Marietas National Park (Anonymous, 2007) and in the Islas Marías Biosphere Reserve (Anonymous, 2007). On the islands of the Mexican Pacific, the National Commission of Natural Protected Areas (CONANP) has also reported its presence in the Islas Marietas National Park (CONANP, 2007) and in the Islas Marías Biosphere Reserve (CONANP, 2007). In Bahía del Rincón, Baja California Sur, giant limpet shells in the intertidal zone have been used as an estimator of algae density and cover due to their

Comentado [jlc1]: Es una referencia?

association with macroalgae (Riosmena-Rodríguez, Hinojosa-Arango, López-Vivas, León-Cisneros, & Holguin-Acosta, 2005). In one of the few studies focusing specifically on the giant Mexican limpet, Ávalos and Méndez (1992) investigate some biological and reproductive aspects of the species on the coast of Michoacan, reporting maximum and minimum sizes, stages of maturity, and stomach contents.

Overexploitation, the dearth of knowledge on this species' biology, and the lack of management strategies for conserving the giant Mexican limpet have caused some populations to decline drastically to the point of nearly disappearing on the Mexican Pacific coast. Currently, the Official Mexican Standard 059 (NOM-059-SEMARNAT-2010) identifies this species as requiring Special Protection (Pr), noting that it is "...threatened by factors that negatively affect its viability, such that it is necessary to promote [this species'] recovery and conservation or the recovery and conservation of associated populations". However, over the last 25 years no biological fishery research has been conducted on this species to estimate its abundance or level of risk on the Mexican Pacific coast. Thus, the goal of the present study is to evaluate the current status of the population of *S. mexicana* on the southern coast of Jalisco, Mexico.

2. Methods

This study was carried out in Bahía de Navidad on the southern coast of Jalisco, Mexico. The bay is delimited to the north by an islet known as El Estrecho and to the south by Punta Graham (between 19°14'N and 104°48'W and 19°10'N and 104°41'W) (Fig. 3). From January through March 2014, a small vessel with a 25 hp outboard motor was chartered for research excursions along the coastline. The research team was composed of two divers experienced in *Octopus hubbsorum* (Berry, 1953) fishing, and therefore well-prepared to dive in the subtidal zone.

Eighteen sampling sites were visited throughout the bay, which was divided into three zones. Zone A to the north included: Ventana del Estrecho, El Estrecho, and Casita (Fig. 3A). In the north-center, Zone B comprised: Palmito, Anegados West, Anegados East, Morro Prieto West, Caleta del Morro Prieto, Morro Prieto East, and Laboratorio (Fig. 3B). Zone C in the south-center included: Virgencita West, Virgencita East, and La Calechosa

(Fig. 3C). Finally, Zone D to the south was composed of: Cuastecomate North, Cuastecomate South, Caleta del Blanco, El Mirador, and Caballito (Fig. 3D).

Two free divers explored each sampling site in parallel following the coastline; each diver searched for specimens in an area measuring approximately 10 m per side. When an organism was located, it was visually verified as the species under study before recording the curve width and curve length of the shell using a tape measure. The depth at which the specimen was found was estimated and the data were recorded on an acrylic board. Next, a photograph was taken of the organism next to a reference scale using a GoPro Hero 3 camera and the geographical position was registered using a GPSmap 60CSx device. The organisms were not extracted from the environment or manipulated in any way. The start time and end time of each dive was recorded in order to calculate the diving time and estimate the catch per unit of effort.

The biometric data were used to generate a size-frequency histogram and a simple linear regression equation. ArcGis 10.2 (Environmental Systems Research Institute, Redlands, CA) was used to create 10 x 10 m polygons encompassing the entire area evaluated at each sampling site based on the start and end data for each dive. The spatial distribution of the organisms was mapped and the sites with the highest density were identified.

3. Results

A total of 404 giant limpets were recorded in 329,720 m² of Bahía de Navidad; the 18 sampling sites were located in exposed rocky areas of the surf zone. The organisms were found from the surface to a maximum depth of 3.5 m. The diving time for each sampling site ranged from 120 to 240 min due to a variety of factors, including accessibility, surf conditions, currents, and the number of organisms found (Table 1). The greatest abundance of giant limpets was found in the central portion of the bay, specifically at Morro Prieto West, Caleta del Morro Prieto, and Virgencita East with 38, 40, and 43 organisms, respectively. In contrast, the lowest abundance was recorded at Laboratorio, La Calechosa, and El Mirador with five, seven, and eight organisms, respectively.

The sampling site with the greatest area covered was El Estrecho, with 73,080 m² and a diving time of 211 min. Thirty-two limpets were recorded, or 9.10 limpets every 60 min

Comentado [jlc2]: Entiendo que es una medida del contorno...no una medida de lado a lado verdad?

Comentado [jlc3]: Mas bien sería registered??

Comentado [jlc4]: Serán autosostenibles?

and 0.09 limpets per 100 m². In contrast, Virgencita West had the lowest total area covered at 6,000 m² and a diving time of 180 min, registering 11 organisms or 3.67 limpets every 60 min and 0.18 limpets per 100 m² (Table 1). A mean of 22.4 specimens were found at each sampling site, or a mean of 0.15 limpets per 100 m² and 7.56 organisms every 60 min. The sampling site with the highest density of organisms was Caleta del Morro Prieto, with a total area covered of 7,800 m² and a diving time of 180 min, registering seven organisms per 100 m². In contrast, Laboratorio and La Calechosa, with a total sampled area of 15,520 and 24,400 m², respectively, had the lowest densities with one organism per 100 m², despite the fact that the diving time was equal to or even greater than that invested at Caleta del Morro Prieto (Figs. 5 and 6).

In this study, specimen sizes ranged from 7 to 26.5 cm curve length and from 5.2 to 24 cm curve width. The 16 cm size class was the most frequent with a total of 84 organisms and a mean curve length of 15.8 cm (Fig. 8). Regarding the biometric relationships between curve length and curve width, a good fit to the linear regression equation was observed. A coefficient of determination of 0.96 was obtained, indicating isometric growth in the range of sizes considered here (Fig. 9).

4. Discussion

New information on the current status of the giant Mexican limpet population in Bahía de Navidad, Jalisco, Mexico, is presented in this study. These data can be used as a baseline for comparison with similar research in other areas of the Pacific, or as a point of reference to assess population trends over time in the study area. To facilitate comparison with future studies, the georeferenced position of each organism was recorded. Moreover, this species is sedentary, exhibiting very limited displacement.

Curve lengths varied considerably, ranging from 7.0 to 26.5 cm; however, the absence of sizes below the minimum reported is notable. This may be due to the difficulty of distinguishing juvenile *S. mexicana* from limpets of other genera that also may be present in the area (e.g., *Lottia* and *Collisella*). Or perhaps small limpets prefer a different habitat. The maximum curve length recorded in this study (26.5 cm) was considerably larger than that reported for Michoacan in 1992 (14.6 cm for females and 15.6 cm for males [Ávalos &

Comentado [jlc5]: Podrías especificar la zona donde hay más si además hay más reclutas

Comentado [jlc6]: Esto debe de ser una prioridad...nosotros haremos lo mismo en el próximo viaje a las Marías

Méndez, 1992]). Moreover, the mean size of the organisms assessed in the present study exceeded the maximum size reported for Michoacan in 1992. In Espinosa and Rivera-Ingraham (2017), Powell (1973) reports the maximum size for the species as 35.5 cm; thus, the sizes observed off the coast of Jalisco in the present study are large.

Comentado [jlc7]: No entiendo, tu rango va ranging from 7.0 to 26.5 cm, y el tamaño mayor reportado en la literatura es de 35.5

The total abundance obtained in this study was 404 organisms in Bahía de Navidad. It is difficult to know how much the population in this area has decreased due to the lack of data. Unfortunately, the National Fisheries Commission's (CONAPESCA) statistical yearbooks of aquaculture and fisheries cannot be used as estimators of abundance relative to previous decades as they do not provide information on this species for Jalisco. For Michoacan and Nayarit, the yearbooks record catches of more than 30 t per year from 1980 to 1983 (CONAPESCA, 1980, 1981, 1982, 1983). However, an annual catch of only 1 t was reported for Michoacan in 1987, reflecting a clear decrease in this resource (CONAPESCA, 1987). It is worth mentioning that this fishing resource is referred to as "limpet" without identifying the species. However, it is assumed that this is the species under consideration due to its size and the reference to catches in Michoacan (Gorrostieta-Hurtado & Trujillo-Toledo, 2012). In their study on the abundance and vertical distribution of gastropods and bivalves in Bahía de Cuastecomate, Jalisco, Esqueda-González et al. (2000) report the presence of the giant Mexican limpet, recording densities of 6 organisms per m² in the lower littoral zone for one of their five sampling sites. In contrast, at La Calechosa, a sample site in the present study located adjacent to Bahía de Cuastecomate, a density of only 1 organism per 100 m² was observed. These results may be taken as a direct reference regarding the abundance of this mollusk in previous decades.

Comentado [jlc8]: Quizás se podría resaltar esto en el resumen del artículo

While anecdotal reports from fishermen are not verifiable data, they offer a general perception of the abundance of this species in the past relative to its current state. Local fishermen were consulted over the course of the present study; all of them agreed that during the 1970s this resource was abundant in the intertidal zone and there were even days when "you didn't even need to get wet to catch this mollusk, they were taken out in heaps". They report that populations have decreased considerably since then to the point that some fishermen consider the species extinct. However, active octopus and lobster fishermen also mentioned that they continue to capture these limpets incidentally, using them primarily for

personal consumption. These anecdotal accounts are in line with published sources noting that the giant limpet is considered extinct for some areas of the Mexican Pacific (Espinosa & Rivera-Ingraham, 2017; Goncalves-Borges, 2013; Ridgway et al., 1998; Simison, 2000). The giant limpet is not mentioned among the species reported in a recent study on commercially important mollusks in Guerrero, Mexico (Galeana-Rebolledo et al., 2018).

Since its creation in 2001, Official Mexican Standard 059 (NOM-059-SEMARNAT-2010) has maintained *S. mexicana* in the category of “Special Protection”. However, this species is not registered as at risk by any international group dedicated to the protection and conservation of fauna and flora. This species is not mentioned by the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) nor is it included on The International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) Red List of Threatened Species. Even more recently, Ramírez-Rodríguez (2013) considered it a species of fishing interest in the snail fishery. This may be due to the dearth of information on this species’ population dynamics over time in the Mexican Pacific and the lack of interest in this resource due to the fact that it is a non-charismatic species (P. Bouchet, pers. comm., November 2011).

Based on the limited available information, it is reasonable to conclude that the giant limpet population has declined at accelerated rates, largely due to anthropogenic causes such as overfishing and the lack of management programs to conserve this resource. In addition, marine invertebrates such as the giant limpet are potentially vulnerable to these environmental changes due to their sessile life condition and their limited or null displacement capacity (Carballo, 2014). Thus, future studies should consider how this species has been affected by recent climate variations and their effects on the ocean such as acidification (Kibria, 2015), and the increases in temperature and sea level (IPCC, 2001, 2007). Globally, all limpet species are considered either threatened or endangered (Espinosa & Rivera-Ingraham, 2017); in particular, *Patella ferruginia* (Gmelin, 1791) is the invertebrate at greatest risk of extinction on the Mediterranean coast (Marra, Andrea De Lucia, Camedda, Espinosa, & Coppa, 2015)

It is urgent that biological studies be carried out on *S. mexicana* with the purpose of understanding this species’ status throughout its distribution in order to update its

protection category under Mexican law and include this species on international threatened species lists. It is equally important to establish urgent protection measures and raise awareness among local fisheries regarding the current state of this limpet species, the largest in the world and considered important since prehispanic times. The results of our study indicate that the giant Mexican limpet is at severe risk of extinction along the southern coast of Jalisco and that if urgent and extreme protection measures are not implemented, its viability as a species may be compromised in the short term.

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Table 1. Total area (square meter) sampled and type of sampling effort, time of diving (minutes), limpets per square meter (Limpets/m²) and limpets each- every 60 minutes (Limpets/ 60 min) used to locate *Scutellastra mexicana* at each sampling site in Bahía de Navidad.

Sites	Nº of Organisms	Total area (m ²)	Time of diving (min)	Limpets / 100 m ²	Limpets /60 min
North zone					
Ventana del					
A Estrecho	13	6240	120	0.21	6.50
B El Estrecho	32	37080	211	0.09	9.10
C Casita	10	18760	150	0.05	4.00
Center zone					
D Palmito	32	22320	165	0.14	11.64
E Anegados	24	11720	135	0.20	10.67
F Anegados este	27	19600	165	0.14	9.82
G Morro prieto oeste	38	20680	210	0.18	10.86
Caleta del Morro					
H prieto	40	7800	180	0.51	13.33
I Morro prieto este	35	16480	240	0.21	8.75
J Laboratorio	5	15520	180	0.03	1.67
K Virgencita oeste	11	6000	180	0.18	3.67
L Virgencita este	43	37000	210	0.12	12.29
M La Calechosa	7	24400	240	0.03	1.75
South zone					
N Cuastecomate norte	25	8000	180	0.28	7.33
Ñ Cuastecomate sur	16	16800	150	0.11	7.60
O Caleta del Blanco	27	29200	180	0.09	9.00
P El Mirador	8	16440	180	0.05	2.67
Q El Caballito	11	15680	120	0.07	5.50
Mean		18318	178	0.15	7.56
Standard deviation		9273.95	35.42	0.11	3.67
Total	404	329720	3196		

Figure legends

Figure 1. Submarine photo of giant mexican limpet (*Scutellastra mexicana*) on the coast of Jalisco, Mexico.

Figure 2. Giant limpet fishermen in the fishing zone of Tehuamixtle, Jalisco, Mexico, in the 1980s.

Figure 3. The study area, Bahía de Navidad, Cihuatlán, Jalisco, Mexico. Sampling sites are indicated with letters.

Figure 4. Relative density of *Scutellastra mexicana* in the northern zone of Bahía de Navidad. Letters indicate specific sampling sites and the corresponding area sampled (ca. 40 m bandwidth). The colored boxes represent the location and number of organisms per 100 m² (area of each box).

Figure 5. Relative density of *Scutellastra mexicana* in the north-central zone of Bahía de Navidad. Letters indicate specific sampling sites and the corresponding area sampled (ca. 40 m bandwidth). The colored boxes represent the location and number of organisms per 100 m² (area of each box).

Figure 6. Relative density of *Scutellastra mexicana* in the south-central zone of Bahía de Navidad. Letters indicate specific sampling sites and the corresponding area sampled (ca. 40 m bandwidth). The colored boxes represent the location and number of organisms per 100 m² (area of each box).

Figure 7. Relative density of *Scutellastra mexicana* in the southern zone of Bahía de Navidad. Letters indicate specific sampling sites and the corresponding area sampled (ca. 40 m bandwidth). The colored boxes represent the location and number of organisms per 100 m² (area of each box).

Figure 8. Size frequency histogram for *Scutellastra mexicana*.

Figure 9. Linear regression model of *Scutellastra mexicana* curve length and curve width.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3 .

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

Figure 9.

Table captions

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